

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Racialised Governance of Migration in Europe

Policy Brief

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Introduction

Migration governance in Europe is often presented as a colour-blind system designed to regulate mobility, manage borders and organise labour markets. However, growing evidence shows that migration policies and labour regimes are embedded in — and actively reproduce — racialised social hierarchies that shape how mobility, belonging and labour are valued.

Across Europe, immigration status, nationality and perceived cultural proximity structure access to residence rights, labour markets and social protection. As a result, irregularity cannot be understood simply as a legal condition. Rather, it must be examined as part of a broader system in which migration governance, labour regimes and public narratives interact to produce and sustain racialised inequalities.

This policy brief draws on the report [Racial Logics of Irregular Migration in Europe: Policy, Perception and Precarity](#), produced within the Horizon Europe and UKRI funded I-CLAIM project. The research examines how race, racism and racialisation shape the production, governance and lived experience of migrant irregularity across six European countries: Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland and the United Kingdom.

Across Europe, racism rarely appears as explicit exclusion. Instead, it operates through institutional arrangements that differentiate access to residence rights, mobility, employment opportunities and social protections. Legal categories, administrative procedures, labour recruitment practices and public narratives collectively produce what the I-CLAIM report describes as a racialised governance of mobility, in which certain groups are systematically positioned as disposable workers and conditional members of society.

Understanding these dynamics is essential for designing migration and labour policies that address migrant precarity while remaining consistent with the European Union's commitments under the [EU Anti-Racism Action Plan 2020–2025](#) and [EU Anti-Racism Strategy 2026–2030](#).

Methodology

This Policy Brief draws on the I-CLAIM comparative report [Racial Logics of Irregular Migration in Europe: Policy, Perception and Precarity](#), examining how race, racism and racialisation shape the production and governance of migrant irregularity across Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland and the United Kingdom.

The findings build on four complementary strands of analysis conducted between 2023 and 2025: legal and policy analysis of migration, labour and welfare frameworks; discourse analysis of a corpus of more than 40,000 texts — including media coverage, parliamentary debates and civil society publications — examining how racialised narratives are constructed; a cross-national survey of 6,322 respondents on public perceptions of irregular migration and immigration enforcement; and qualitative fieldwork comprising 244 interviews and observations with migrant workers and stakeholders in agriculture, domestic work and food delivery.

Main research findings

MAIN FINDING #1:

Racialised legal and policy infrastructures

Race plays a pivotal role in determining who is irregularised, who is granted rights, and who is excluded from legal, labour, and social protections.

While EU equality law formally prohibits discrimination on the grounds of race or ethnicity, it largely excludes immigration status and nationality from these protections. As a result, migration governance has emerged as the primary domain where racialisation is not only most visible but also where assumed racial hierarchies are actively produced and reinforced ([EU 2020](#)).

Visa regimes, employer-linked residence permits, welfare conditionality and discretionary administrative practices create differentiated pathways into regularity and irregularity. These mechanisms produce hierarchies of belonging in which migrants from certain regions or backgrounds face greater bureaucratic obstacles and insecurity.

Irregularity therefore emerges not simply as the absence of immigration status but as the outcome of institutional arrangements that differentially value mobility and labour.

MAIN FINDING #2:

Racialised narratives in political and media discourse

Migration governance is also shaped by narratives that construct migrants through racialised and culturalised representations.

Across European media and political debates, irregularised migrants are frequently portrayed through proxy categories such as nationality, religion, gender and behaviour. These proxies substitute for explicit references to race while still conveying racialised meanings.

For example, representations of “dangerous male migrants” often draw on associations with specific regions such as North Africa or the Middle East, linking masculinity, migration and perceived security threats. These narratives contribute to moral hierarchies that distinguish between “deserving” and “undeserving” migrants.

MAIN FINDING #3:

Racialised perceptions and public attitudes

Public perceptions of irregular migration reflect and reinforce these narratives.

Survey findings show that perceptions of migrants’ economic contribution, cultural compatibility and trustworthiness are often shaped by racialised assumptions about nationality, religion and

ethnicity. These perceptions influence hiring practices, policy preferences and everyday interactions between migrants and host societies.

They also shape institutional practices, including policing, workplace inspections and access to services.

In many cases, racially minoritised EU minorities — including Roma communities — experience forms of surveillance and exclusion similar to those directed at migrants with insecure statuses, demonstrating how racism can blur the boundaries between migration status and social exclusion.

MAIN FINDING #4:**Agriculture: racialised labour segmentation**

In the agricultural sector, racialisation operates primarily through labour segmentation.

Workers are often ranked according to nationality and perceived proximity to the national majority. Recruitment practices frequently rely on stereotypes about productivity, reliability or cultural compatibility, leading to the concentration of particular groups in the most precarious roles.

Seasonal migration schemes and subcontracting arrangements reinforce these hierarchies by tying workers' legal status to specific employers or recruitment intermediaries.

These arrangements allow employers to transform legal precarity into a labour management strategy, ensuring a workforce that is flexible, replaceable and less able to challenge exploitative working conditions.

MAIN FINDING #5:**Food delivery: visibility and algorithmic control**

The food delivery sector illustrates how racialisation interacts with digital labour platforms.

Although platform work is often framed as flexible and autonomous, algorithmic systems determine access to shifts, allocate orders and monitor performance. These systems can reproduce existing inequalities by penalising workers with fewer resources or uncertain and short-term immigration status.

Customer ratings and digital identity verification can also reproduce biases related to accent, appearance or perceived cultural proximity.

Because delivery work takes place in public space, migrant riders are highly visible and may face more frequent identity checks, police harassment or immigration enforcement actions.

Together, algorithmic management, public visibility and immigration control produce a particularly intense form of racialised labour discipline.

MAIN FINDING #6:**Domestic work: racialisation through intimacy and care**

Domestic work is shaped by different racialised dynamics linked to the private nature of the workplace.

Employers often rely on cultural stereotypes about trust, care and obedience when selecting domestic workers. These perceptions shape recruitment practices and contribute to the concentration of migrant women from particular regions in domestic and care work.

Because the workplace is a private household, labour protections are often weaker and oversight more limited. Migrant domestic workers may therefore face exploitative working conditions, excessive hours and dependence on employers for housing or documentation.

In this sector, race, gender and migration status intersect to produce particularly vulnerable forms of labour.

Policy recommendations

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #1:**Integrate migration governance into the EU Anti-Racism Strategy**

Migration governance should be recognised as a key domain in which structural racism can emerge through policy design and implementation. While the EU Anti-Racism Action Plan 2020–2025 and the EU Anti-Racism Strategy 2026–2030 acknowledge the structural nature of racism, migration policies themselves remain only partially addressed.

The European Commission should therefore ensure that migration governance is explicitly considered in the implementation of the 2026-2030 Anti-Racism Strategy. This includes ensuring through the monitoring of National Action Plans Against Racism (NAPARs) that immigration laws, visa regimes and residence policies do not produce differentiated access to rights and protection.

Key measures could include:

- conducting racial equality impact assessments of migration policies at EU and national levels;
- strengthening the role of national equality bodies in addressing discrimination linked to immigration enforcement and administrative practices;
- incorporating migration governance within the monitoring framework of the EU Anti-Racism Strategy.
- Withdrawing the proposed Returns Regulation which produces a deportation and detention regime that will disproportionately impact racialised migrants, in particular those who are irregularised as a result of administrative and state policies.

A growing body of research and policy analysis highlights the importance of addressing migration governance within anti-racism policy frameworks ([CERD 2023](#); [ENAR 2023, 2025](#); [PICUM 2025](#)).

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #2:**Address racialised narratives shaping migration governance**

Public narratives play an important role in shaping migration policies. Migrants are often represented through proxy categories — such as nationality, religion or cultural difference — that reproduce racialised distinctions without explicit reference to race.

National governments, European institutions and funding bodies should strengthen efforts to monitor and challenge discriminatory narratives surrounding migration.

This could include:

- Supporting independent monitoring of migration discourse in media and political debate;
- Promoting evidence-based communication strategies in the implementation of the EU Pact on Migration and Asylum;
- Supporting research and civil society initiatives, with the direct involvement of racialised migrant communities, that document the impact of racialised narratives on public attitudes and policymaking.

Addressing these narratives is essential to implementing the objectives of the EU Anti-Racism Strategy and strengthening trust in public institutions.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #3:**Strengthen safeguards against racial profiling in migration enforcement**

Evidence from across Europe indicates that racialised minorities and migrants are disproportionately affected by identity checks, policing practices and immigration enforcement.

EU and national policymakers should strengthen mechanisms that prevent discriminatory enforcement practices and ensure accountability where they occur.

Policy priorities include:

- Establishing independent oversight mechanisms for immigration enforcement practices;
- Improving data collection on discriminatory policing and migration enforcement;
- Ensuring that victims of discrimination can report abuses without fear of immigration consequences.

Recent studies and civil society reports have highlighted concerns about racial profiling in identity checks and internal border controls within the Schengen area².

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #4:**Reform labour migration systems that produce structural dependency**

Labour migration policies across Europe often rely on employer-linked visas and temporary migration schemes, particularly in sectors such as agriculture and care work. These arrangements create structural dependency on employers and increase workers' vulnerability to exploitation.

EU institutions and member states should review labour migration frameworks to ensure that migrant workers can exercise labour rights without risking the loss of their residence status.

Priority actions include:

- Allowing migrant workers to change employers without losing their residence permits;
- strengthening enforcement mechanisms under the [Employer Sanctions Directive](#) (2009/52/EC);
- Improving cooperation between labour inspectorates, equality bodies and worker organisations.
- Opening up regularisation pathways for migrant workers, not tied to a specific employer.

Strengthening labour protections for migrant workers is essential for addressing labour exploitation, preventing the emergence of racially segmented labour markets and ensuring that all workers and employees contribute equitably to taxes and public revenues. Labour protections would not only safeguard migrant workers but also uplift conditions for the entire working population, fostering fairness and economic resilience for all.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #5:**Ensure that platform work regulation protects migrant workers**

Digital labour platforms increasingly rely on migrant workers, particularly in sectors such as food delivery.

Although platform work is often framed as flexible and accessible, workers frequently face precarious working conditions, algorithmic management and limited access to labour protections.

The transposition of the [EU Platform Work Directive](#) (2024) into national law by the end of 2026 provides an opportunity to ensure that platform regulation adequately protects migrant workers¹.

EU and national policymakers should therefore:

- Guarantee labour rights regardless of migration status;
- Ensure transparency and oversight of algorithmic management systems;
- Prevent digital identity verification systems from being used as tools of immigration enforcement.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #6:

¹<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2024/2831/oj/eng>

Strengthen labour protections for migrant domestic workers

Domestic work remains one of the least regulated sectors of the European labour market despite its central role in sustaining European care systems.

Migrant women represent a large proportion of domestic workers and often experience intersecting vulnerabilities linked to gender, migration status and racialisation.

EU and national policymakers should:

- Strengthen labour protections in line with [ILO Convention No. 189 on Domestic Workers](#);
- Introduce labour inspection mechanisms adapted to household workplaces, while ensuring they operate entirely independently of immigration enforcement;
- Support collective organisation and access to trade unions for domestic workers, regardless of their immigration status.

Improving labour protections in this sector is also consistent with the objectives of the [European Care Strategy](#), which aims to improve working conditions across care sectors.

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